

VETERINARY SCIENCES

THE DURATION OF THE EGG LAYING SEASON OF THE INDIGENOUS MACEDONIAN „KAMENJARKA“ HEN

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Abstract

To date, Macedonia does not have any officially recognized and internationally registered chicken breed, as can be seen from Lukanov's voluminous, comprehensive monograph [2].

Nevertheless, the question arises whether it is possible that no indigenous breed or at least species of chickens has ever developed in Macedonian territory. This seems highly improbable, bearing in mind that people in Macedonia have been keeping chickens and breeding them for egg and meat production for centuries. Apart from that, it is a known fact that poultry farming is the fastest of all types of livestock production, as flock renewal and production are faster than in other common animals. In addition, primitive chickens foraged in the wild and did not need any supplementary feed. They were also highly resistant to harsh climatic conditions and changes.

Keywords: “Kamenjarka”, hen, chicken, rooster, Macedonian heritage, egg laying time, poultry, eggs.

As mentioned by Oberhofer [3] in his 1929 book on poultry farming, which was exceptional for that time, every one of our regions (i.e. the then state) had its own domestic chicken. This speaks for the Macedonian author's present-day theses and arguments in favor of the "Kamenjarka" being old breed of chicken. Oberhofer states that these domestic hens differ in body size and feather colour, with white being the most common. Pavlović [4] also notes that the domestic hen is widespread, weighing between 1.2 and 2.0 kg. According to him, its feather colour can be entirely black or white, as well as show any possible combination of these two colours.

To date, Karov and Kolev [1] are most likely to be the only authors that mention the Macedonian “Kamenjarka” in scientific literature, stating that it is an indigenous breed of bird originating from south-east Asia, which came to Macedonia around 2000 BC.

Chickens of this breed live in the open space. They hide from predators in trees, where they also sleep throughout the year.

The authors note that the hen weighs up to 2kg, while the rooster can weigh up to 2.5kg. The meat has a dark colour.

Due to the fact that there is no data on egg production of this breed in the available scientific literature, a one-year study of 20 privately owned laying hens was carried out. It goes without saying that this number of

hens is not sufficient in order to draw any detailed, complex conclusions. However, bearing in mind that it is rather hard to keep these hens in an organized group so that they do not leave a limited area, the study results can be considered the first actually relevant ones.

Author's study

Twenty adult “Kamenjarka” hens were kept in a fenced area of 400 m², where they could move freely. They ground was grass, with many dense shrubs here and there.

The hens laid their first eggs at the age of 6 to 7 months, so that hens born in one year would lay eggs in the next. When exactly they start laying depends on the weather, but most often it is in the second half of January. However, if a hen is laying eggs for the first time, it may start a little later when it gets warmer. A biological mechanism determines the time when hens lay so that they can start throughout the year, providing for households to always have eggs.

The hens lay one egg a day, some always in the same place, but most of them in several places, so that all places have to be checked when collecting the eggs. The laying time is around midday, which may be due to the fact that it is harder for people to find the eggs in the evening when it is getting dark. Also, predators are more active in the evenings, so that eggs should be collected before they can find them.

Pic.1 Rooster

Pic.2 Hen

The breeding instinct of the “Kamenjarka” can be described as well developed. Twice a year, it lies in a "nest" and hatches eggs. However, one can hardly call this a genuine, classic nest as found in cultivated chicken breeds, but rather a roosting place with collected grass around it. We should point out that the rooster protects the hen while she incubates the eggs. The optimal number of eggs on which the hen broods is 15. Due to her small body size, she cannot keep more eggs warm and protected. Therefore, the “Kamenjarka” breeds twice a year, thus doubling the low number of eggs in a clutch.

During one year, the “Kamenjarka” does not lay very many eggs, about 180. This number is not large,

but usually no-one counted these hens on farms, since their number was large enough so that there were always enough eggs for domestic use throughout the year, following the principle of "minimum investment for maximum return".

Conclusion

The “Kamenjarka” is certainly not a chicken breed worth breeding for mass production of meat and eggs, as it is not very fleshy and does not lay many eggs. However, it is precious as a genetic resource and as a resilient breed adapted to the regional climatic conditions. It should be preserved as Macedonian heritage in the field of livestock breeding.

Pic.3 Hen (left) and rooster (right)

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